

Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement

How to use the Evaluation Tool

A guide for Students

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AsCOLA is an acronym which stands for “Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement”. An Erasmus+ Key Action 2 project, AsCOLA aims to enhance and digitalize the quality framework of Erasmus+ student mobility and contribute to closing the data gap in the quality aspect of higher education transformation. The project will help higher education institutions (HEIs) better monitor and assess their institutional performance in education activities related to their internationalization strategy and policy.

The project will achieve these objectives through multiple activities, namely:

- a) Creating an evaluation methodology of the courses offered to Erasmus+ students.
- b) Developing and piloting an online evaluation tool connected to the Online Learning Agreement.
- c) Carrying out training sessions and producing train-the-trainers material to equip HEIs with the necessary knowledge to use the tool effectively.

In this guide “How to use the evaluation tool”, we will discuss how you can use the tool as a student. We will explain all steps and include screenshots for clarification.

Note: For the time being, course evaluations will only be available for you as a student if your Higher Education Institution uses the Online Learning Agreement. For more information, contact the International Relations Office of your institution.

How to log-in

a) Go to <https://ascola.eu/login>. You will be directed to the homepage of the tool where you can log-in.

AsCOLA

ABOUT LOG IN

AsCOLA

Browse reviews and evaluate courses
of your mobility exchange.

Log in with MyAcademicID

Your Evaluation is just a click away!

The login options available to access the AsCOLA platform are the following:

- eduGAIN (your academic credentials)
- eIDAS (national ID)
- Google login

- b) First time logging in? Log-in with your **MyAcademic ID or create one** by first selecting your institution and then filling out your login.

MyAcademicID

Login with

Examples: University of Bologna, name@aut

or

Login with eIDAS

Login with Google

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- c) Complete the **registration steps** as presented on the screen. This includes providing background information about yourself, as part of the registration.

The screenshot shows the MyAcademicID logo at the top, which consists of a circular icon made of concentric lines in blue and orange, followed by the text "MyAcademicID" in blue and orange. Below the logo is a light orange box containing the following text:

The MyAcademicID IAM Service is used to access all Erasmus mobility services. Since November 2020 all users are required to complete the registration on the MyAcademicID IAM Service in order to continue.

You will have to complete the following steps:

1. **Click on "Proceed to register on the MyAcademicID IAM Service"**
2. **Fill in the registration form.** To be able to view and process your previous OLA, use the email that you had used before.
3. **You will receive an e-mail to verify your e-mail address.**
4. **Click on the verification link in that email to complete the registration.**

At the bottom of the screenshot is a dark blue button with the text "Proceed to register on the MyAcademicID IAM Service" in white.

How to navigate

- a) Once you are registered, you're redirected to 'My evaluations'. Here you can find the **list of courses** of your finalized Online Learning Agreement(s).
- b) You can also **browse through existing evaluations** of exchange courses to help you decide on the courses you want to apply for. **Note:** only exchange courses from Higher Education Institutions that agreed to display their courses in the tool are visible.
- c) Use the top left menu to switch between:
 1. Your **own evaluations**, to create and edit;
 2. And **all evaluations**, to browse through evaluations from courses you want to apply for.

ABOUT LOG OUT

My evaluations

Here you can find the list of courses of the Online Learning Agreement you took in exchange. Provide feedback by clicking on the 'Create new evaluation' button in the last column. You can also edit or delete previously submitted evaluations, by clicking on the 'Edit' icon . If you are academic staff of an HEI or future exchange student looking for more info about the courses, please visit [All Evaluations](#).

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS	
Mathematics	1234	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5	Create new evaluation
a	1	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	1	Create new evaluation
a	a	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	4	Create new evaluation
zzz	zzz	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	3	Create new evaluation
a	a	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	1	Create new evaluation

How to browse through course evaluations

- In the top left corner, choose “**all evaluations**”.
- Find specific courses** by entering the exact course title or the course code (be sure to switch to ‘search by course code’ using the button below). **Note:** not all Higher Education Institutions will provide access to their evaluations, it is therefore possible you won’t be able to find certain courses in the list.

Note: Not all HEIs allow their evaluations to be visible through this tool.

AsCOLA ABOUT LOG OUT

All evaluations

Here you can browse courses evaluations. Search by entering the exact full title of the course or the course code, click on the class you're interested in and access feedback submitted by previous exchange students.

Enter exact full course title or use the switch to search by course code

Search by course code

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS
Business Administration	BA100-01	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5
HTML I	HTML01	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	6
Math	1567	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	6
Mathematics	1234	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5
Mathematics II	MATH-102	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	0
Mathematics for Computer Science	MATH-1010	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5
Programming Languages I	PL123	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5

Rows per page: 10 1-7 of 7

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- a) **Select a course** you want to view the evaluation data of and click on the course.
- b) You are now able to see the evaluation results. The evaluation results are presented per **theme** in a list.

The screenshot shows the AsCOLA website interface. At the top left is the AsCOLA logo. At the top right are links for 'ABOUT' and 'LOG OUT'. The main content area is titled 'Course evaluations' and contains a table with the following data:

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS	INSTITUTION
Business Administration	BA100-01	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5	uni-foundation.eu

Below the table, there is a list of evaluation themes, each with a dropdown arrow:

- Background info
- General impression
- Learning methods
- Teachers
- Cultural differences

- c) Click on a **theme bar** to open the results.
TIP: Be sure to scroll all the way down to not miss anything.
- d) All outcomes **per statement, per topic** are presented here. Statements are answered with 5 different answer options (see corresponding colors).
- e) The **numbers in the bars** show the number of students that chose this answer option.

Course evaluations

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS	INSTITUTION
Business Administration	BA100-01	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5	uni-foundation.eu

Background info

General impression

Legend: Strongly disagree (red), Disagree (orange), Neutral (yellow), Agree (green), Strongly agree (blue)

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The overall quality of the course was sufficient	2	3	6	3	1
The course was well organized	1	2	6	3	3
The course subject matter was adapted to my prior knowledge	7	5	1	1	1
The course objectives were clear to me	1	5	5	1	1
The relevance of the topics of this course within the context of my field of study was clear to me	1	2	7	4	1
The learning management system was clearly structured	2	5	6	2	2

How to provide feedback about your OLA courses (create, edit and delete evaluations)

a) Fill out the evaluations for the courses you took part in during your exchange via the **'my evaluations page'**.

My evaluations

All evaluations

My account

ABOUT LOG OUT

My evaluations

Here you can find the list of courses of the Online Learning Agreement you took in exchange. Provide feedback by clicking on the 'Create new evaluation' button in the last column. You can also edit or delete previously submitted evaluations, by clicking on the 'Edit' icon . If you are academic staff of an HEI or future exchange student looking for more info about the courses, please visit [All Evaluations](#).

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS	
Mathematics	1234	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	5	Create new evaluation
a	1	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	1	Create new evaluation
a	a	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	4	Create new evaluation
ZZZ	ZZZ	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	3	Create new evaluation
a	a	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	1	Create new evaluation

- b) You can create a **new evaluation** by clicking the 'add' icon next to the course title.
- c) You can **edit** previously submitted evaluations by clicking the 'edit' icon or **delete** them by clicking the 'delete' icon.

Previously submitted evaluations can be found at the bottom of the list/table.

ABOUT

LOG OUT

My evaluations

Here you can find the list of courses of the Online Learning Agreement you took in exchange. Provide feedback by clicking on the 'Create new evaluation' button in the last column. You can also edit or delete previously submitted evaluations, by clicking on the 'Edit' icon . If you are academic staff of an HEI or future exchange student looking for more info about the courses, please visit [All Evaluations](#).

COURSE TITLE	COURSE CODE	ACADEMIC TERM	ECTS	
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a	a	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	1	Create new evaluation
aaa	aaa	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	5	Create new evaluation
a	a	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	1	Create new evaluation

d) **Fill out the questions** per page and click 'Next Step'. You can go back to the previous page by clicking 'Previous'.

The screenshot shows a survey page titled "General impression of the course". At the top, there is a progress bar with 9 steps, where step 2 is currently active. The survey consists of six statements, each with a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree". The "Next Step" button is highlighted with a red box.

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The overall quality of the course was sufficient *	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course was well organized *	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course subject matter was adapted to my prior knowledge *	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course objectives were clear to me *	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The relevance of the topics of this course within the context of my field of study was clear to me *	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The learning management system was clearly structured *	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Note: You are required to fill out all questions marked with (*) before you can go to the next page.

Note: Questions with radio buttons (round bullets, left image) allow one answer; questions with checkboxes (square bullets, right image) allow for multiple answers.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What are your main motives to participate in this course? *

- Academic opportunities
- Experiencing different cultures
- Career advancement
- Quality of education
- Personal motives
- Other, namely

e) Any further explanations or comments can be left in the **open comment fields** per topic.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the AsCOLA evaluation interface. The page title is "Cultural differences/issues". It features a progress bar at the top with 8 steps, where the current step is highlighted. Below the title, there are five survey questions, each with a five-point Likert scale (Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly agree). The questions are:

- Input from an international perspective was valued in the course *
- The course provided me with opportunities to share my thoughts and feelings *
- The learning activities allowed for contact with other local/exchange students *
- I experienced no cultural obstacles in the course *
- I experienced no language obstacles/barriers in the course *

Below the survey questions, there is a text input field with the prompt: "Please share your experiences with the cultural differences or issues you encountered in the course." This field is highlighted with a red border. At the bottom of the page, there are "Previous" and "Next Step" buttons. The footer includes the European Union logo and the text "Co-funded by the European Union".

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- f) When you've filled out all questions from the survey, **submit** your evaluation by clicking on the 'Submit' button at the last step.

The screenshot displays the AsCOLA survey interface. At the top left is the AsCOLA logo and a menu icon. At the top right are links for 'ABOUT' and 'LOG OUT'. A progress bar at the top shows 10 steps, with the 10th step being the current one. The main content area has a blue-to-purple gradient background and is titled 'Final Question'. Below the title is a text input field with the prompt: 'Are there any other personal thoughts and experiences as an exchange student you would like to share with us?'. At the bottom of the input area are two buttons: 'Previous' and 'Submit'. The 'Submit' button is highlighted with a red rectangular box. At the bottom of the page, there is a black footer containing the European Union flag, the text 'Co-funded by the European Union', and a disclaimer: 'The European Commission's support for the production of this 'publication' does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only from the authors and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.'

- g) The **submitted evaluations** can be found by clicking on 'My evaluations' (at the end of the list) and can be edited or deleted there.